

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D1.3

Project Activity Report Year 1

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
API	Application Program Interface
C-SCALE	Copernicus - eoSC Analytics Engine
CA	Consortium Agreement
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche
DICE	Data Infrastructure Capacity for EOSC
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Council
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EGI-ACE	EGI Advanced Computing for EOSC
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESI	Expert Systems Iberia
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible
IM	Innovation Manager
INGV	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
IP	Intellectual Property
ISMAR	Istituto di Scienze Marine
MEEO	Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation
MS	Milestone
PM	Problem management
PMT	Project management Team
PSC	Project Steering Committee
PSNC	Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
RELIANCE	Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO	Research Objects
T2	Terradue
TC	Technical Coordinator
TL	Task Leaders
UiO	Universitetet i Oslo
UPM	Polytechnic University of Madrid (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)
VO	Virtual Organization
WP	Work package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

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1 Executive Summary

RELIANCE, short for Research Lifecycle Management for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC, aims to realize the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic research management approach based on three key and complementary technologies: i) Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities, which relies upon ROHub platform as the reference service; ii) data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access, which relies upon the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform as the reference service; iii) text mining and semantic enrichment services allowing to extract machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research, and which rely on the AI-based platform Cogito as base system. As part of the integration in EOSC, RELIANCE services will leverage and integrate with some of the EOSC core cross-cutting and added-value services (as described in this document), playing a complementary role to what is already available and bridging between various EOSC services. RELIANCE will pilot the services in three different Earth Science communities, fostering the use of Copernicus data and demonstrating their efficacy in real-life vertical and multi-disciplinary scenarios, and will launch an Open Call to engage other communities.

This document is the yearly activity report of RELIANCE for the first year of the project. The report comprises a detailed description of the activities carried out by each task in each work package, covering all the administrative, technical, integration, innovation, IPR and data management aspects. A second report will be delivered at the end of the second year.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope

The RELIANCE project has two mandatory reporting periods covering M1-M12, M13-M24. In addition to periodic and final reports to be submitted to the Project Officer (PO), this reporting has been set up, in order to ensure that all project obligations (as stated in the DoA, Part B) are being fulfilled, and the progress of each Work Package is documented and on track.

The practice of regular reporting and updating of all partners relies on an established procedure: every two weeks, there is a consortium meeting, where all partners report on their progress, updates, and any issues they are facing. Additional information may be requested via ad-hoc meetings or email as necessary. Moreover, the project carries out regular plenaries (3 last year including the KoM), where one or two days are dedicated to discuss the progress in each Work Package, among others. The collected information is used to prepare the activity reports which have been set as deliverables covering 2 periods for the two years of the project.

The deliverable includes a report organized by Work Package. For each Work Package, first a summary report is provided, and then more details are provided for each task, including i) a summary of the task progress, ii) the significant results for this period, iii) risks, deviations from the description of action and corrective actions taken/suggested, and iv) the next steps in next period.

This deliverable describes the activities carried out in the RELIANCE project during the first year of the project, covering all the administrative, technical, integration, innovation, IPR and data management perspectives.

In the first year of the project, the consortium carried out the tasks to set up appropriate teams, discuss inter-relations and dependencies between the Work Packages in order to work better together

and reduce the number of overlaps, achieve the first milestones in each task and deliver the work promised in the GA for the first year of the project.

The consortium carried out bi-weekly meetings, every second Thursday at 11am, and had three consortium meetings: the KoM on 13th and 14th January 2021, a plenary meeting on the 3rd August 2021, and on the 9th December 2021. Additionally, the steering committee and work package leaders met with the External Advisory Board on 8th September 2021. For year one, RELIANCE Project planned and delivered a total of 19 Deliverables, achieving the first 5 milestones, as presented in Table 1 and 2, respectively.

Due to a significant number of deliverables being scheduled for M12 (which coincided with the holiday period as the project started in January 2021), some of the processes were slower than expected. This resulted in some delays, although all of them were delivered within 2-3 weeks later, with the exception of two of them (namely D1.3 – this document, and D2.7) that were officially shifted with the approval of the PO, as described more in detail in the WP reports. Similarly, all milestones were achieved successfully, except from the launch of the open call which was shifted as well together with D2.7.

Table 1 List of RELIANCE deliverables for year 1

Del. N°	Deliverable name	WP	lead participant	Type	Diss. level	Del. Date
D1.1	Project Management Handbook	WP1	PSNC	R	PU	M2
D1.2	Initial Data Management Plan	WP1	PSNC	ORDP	PU	M6
D1.3	Project Activity Report Year	WP1	PSNC	R	PU	M12
D2.1	Business plan & exploitation strategy - Issue 1	WP2	ALPHA	R	CO	M12
D2.3	Project communication Plan	WP2	T2	R	PU	M3
D2.4	Report on communication and dissemination materials and events Issue 1	WP2	T2	R	PU	M12
D2.7	Report on Epistemic communities' cooperation and networking	WP2	ALPHA	R	PU	M12
D3.1	Semantic resources	WP3	ESI	R	PU	M4
D3.2	Design, implementation and deployment of text mining and enrichment services Phase 1	WP3	ESI	R	PUB	M12
D4.1	Data Cube metadata model	WP4	UPM	R	PU	M4
D4.2	Data Cube API – Release I	WP4	MEE0	R	PU	M6
D4.4	FAIR Data Cubes – Release I	WP4	MEE0	R	PU	M6
D4.5	FAIR Data Cubes – Release II	WP4	MEE0	R	PU	M12
D5.1	RO model adapted to EOSC	WP5	UPM	R	PU	M4
D5.2	Design, implementation and deployment of research object services, phase I	WP5	PSNC	R	PU	M12
D6.1	EOSC Integration Plan	WP6	PSNC	R	PU	M3
D6.2	Annual report on EOSC Operation – Year 1	WP6	T2	R	PU	M12

D6.4	Copernicus Data Pipelines Report – Year 1	WP6	T2	R	PU	M12
D7.1	Report on Earth Science multidisciplinary case study on 2020 lockdown: requirements, testing, demonstration and population	WP7	CNR	R	PU	M12

Table 2 List of RELIANCE milestones for year 1

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related work package(s)	Due date (in month)	Means of verification
MS1	Kick - Off	WP1	M1	Project started, kick-off meeting, all activities due to start at M1 are effectively started
MS2	Early onboarding, communication plan & project management setup	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	M3	Internal communication tool set up, web portal launched, onboarding of services. D1.1, D2.3 D6.1
MS3	Model and resources adaptation to EOSC	WP3, WP4, WP5	M4	D3.1, D4.1, D5.1
MS4	Data management plan and initial data cubes	WP1, WP4	M6	D1.2, D4.2, D4.4
MS5	RELIANCE services in EOSC v1, outreach & multi-disciplinary research, Open call	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	M12	D2.1, D2.4, D2.6, D3.2, D4.5, D5.2, D6.2, D6.4, D7.1

In addition to achieving all of these targets, RELIANCE has been very active during the first year regarding its participation and contribution to different working groups and task forces in EOSC, as well as regarding its collaboration with other EOSC related projects, with a major focus on other InfraEOSC07 projects and the EOSC Future project. Some of these activities include:

- InfraEOSC-07 joined action to specify in more detail the EOSC Virtual Access mechanisms with the EC.
- Definition of the categories and teams of collaboration of InfraEOSC-07 projects and EOSC Future, including technical activities, uptake and training.
- Contribution to the specification of the EOSC Future & INFRAEOSC-07-2020 Collaboration Agreement
- Support of the first EOSC Future demo to EC about the integration of services in EOSC, showcasing some of the RELIANCE services.
- Participation in the EOSC Task Force Charter - Semantic Interoperability. RELIANCE scientific coordinator - SC (Oscar Corcho) is co-leading this Task Force. The task force has three sub-groups, where both SC and the project coordinator – PC (Raul Palma) participate:
 - Theme 1: Metadata standards
 - Theme 2: Metadata catalogues
 - Theme 3: Use cases
- Participation in the Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group – WG
- Participation in the Compute Continuum Working Group – WG
- Participation in the technical alignment with EOSC science projects
 - RELIANCE will help shepherding some of these projects like SSHOC, EOSC-life, and ENVRI-FAIR

- Contribution to the EOSC Multiannual Roadmap (MAR) 2023-2024
- Contribution to the EOSC Future MVE Functions for D2.9
- Contribution in the identification of EOSC Horizontal Services and automated access to IT resources (Feb 2022)
- Support first EOSC Ask Me Anything Session, led by DICE, with RELIANCE use cases (Feb 2022)
- Bilateral meetings with other InfraEOSC-07 projects for collaboration including DICE, OpenAire and EGI.

2.2 Audience

This deliverable is intended for an external audience, including other EOSC related projects who are also dealing with the integration of their services into the EOSC.

2.3 Structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 3 includes the activity reports. For each Work Package a general summary is provided, followed by a detailed information per task, with the list of key achievement, risks and deviations, and plans for the next period
- Section 4 provides general conclusions of the work carried out during the first year

3 Progress and activity reports per WP

3.1 WP1 – Project management and coordination

During the first 12 months of the project WP1 carried out all the activities necessary to ensure an effective and efficient implementation of the project, including:

- Provision of top-level management of the project to ensure that RELIANCE objectives were met on time
- Facilitating the communication and integration between partners
- Providing effective reporting and communication within project and the European Commission and other external actors, particularly related to the EOSC ecosystem (e.g., other InfraEOSC07 projects, EOSC Future project, EOSC Working groups)
- Giving the technical and administrative support to partners and to the project committees/boards in the preparation and execution of major project meetings and obligations
- Provision of the project handbook, including information about the communication tools and channels, templates, meetings and other management procedures supporting the project execution
- The design, development and deployment of RELIANCE Website
- Provision of the project's Data Management Plan (DMP)

3.1.1 Task 1.1

Task	Title
1.1	Administrative & Financial Management
Contributors	PSNC, all
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
During the first year of the project, task 1.1 carried out the project coordination to guarantee the agreed communication procedures and document distribution based on well-defined templates,	

time and resource control against the deliverables, progress reporting to the commission and organising plenary meetings. This task was responsible for creating the Consortium Agreement and produced deliverable D1.1 - project management handbook, which describes all the necessary information to support the management of the RELIANCE project, including project management principles and instruments, the implementation plan, the organisational structure, the collaboration and communication tools, task forces, meetings and other management procedures, as well as quality assurance procedures, the deliverable production and review process. As part of this task, PSNC deployed/configured the following communication tools and channels:

- email & mailing lists (for internal communication, and for users' support)
- social media accounts (twitter, linkedin)
- conferencing system for the regular meetings
- collaborative workspace for partners (wiki style)
- cloud storage and file hosting for partners
- issue tracker for partners

Additionally, this task was responsible for the design and implementation of the project logo and templates (for deliverables and presentations), as well as the project Website. Moreover, this task produced three professional introductory promotional videos of RELIANCE (which were not planned in the proposal).

This task has also been responsible for organising project meetings, this includes the Kick-Off meeting, and two plenary meetings during the first year of the project. Additionally, this task is responsible for organising the regular bi-weekly meeting where all partners participate. All the meetings have taken place online due to the COVID-19 situation. This task also helped setting up the task forces identified in the kick-off meeting, which boosted some horizontal actions at the beginning of the project.

Finally, this task managed all financial aspects of the project, including the provision of templates for partners to submit their periodic activity (by WP) and financial reports, the preparation of an internal payment procedure, the creation and update of a list of bank accounts of all the partners, as well as handling all communications with the EU Commission regarding the agreed actions, and uploading of deliverables and other information in the EC portal.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- D1.1 Project Management Handbook
- RELIANCE mailing lists (general one: reliance@lists.man.poznan.pl)
- Project Logo and templates
- Project Website (<https://www.reliance-project.eu/>)
- social media channels: https://twitter.com/reliance_eosc
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/reliance-project/about/>
- conference system (PSNC WebEx)
- collaborative space: <https://docs.psnk.pl/display/RELIANCE/RELIANCE>
- cloud storage & file hosting: <https://box.pionier.net.pl/d/9d7a70133a514a95ad8a/>
- issue tracker: <https://support.pcsc.pl/projects/RELIANCE>
- RELIANCE introductory promo videos (see on Website)

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

This task undertook heavier workload than anticipated with the design and deployment of the Website, and the creation of professional videos. No risks were identified during this period. Regarding deviations, this document (D1.3) was shifted from M12 to M13, as it was intended to cover all activities until M12 for each Work Package. The change was agreed with the PO, and the new date was updated in the EC portal.

Next Steps in Next Period

In the next period this task will continue the project coordination, and in particular the first part of the next period will be dedicated to the creation and submission of the official reports to the EU commission, including handling all the communications and requests received, and the financial aspects of the project for the second payment to the partners. This task will also continue the management and update of the project Website, and organisation of the next plenary meeting and bi-weekly meetings.

3.1.1 Task 1.2

Task	Title
1.2	Scientific and Technical Coordination
Contributors	PSNC, all
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project, task 1.2 has worked on the project scientific strategy, monitoring the impact of results in scientific communities and implementing initial tasks for engaging and leveraging the EOSC ecosystem, as well as analysing the technology and development strategy, coordinating the technical activities between all WPs, focussing on the technology integration activities in EOSC, which are a core outcome of the project.</p> <p>In particular, the TC in collaboration with the PC coordinated the overall technical development of the project, including the definition of the technology and development strategy, the technical activities between all work packages, working with WP leaders to plan, monitor and direct all general technical aspects, ensuring that all technical milestones were met. As a result, all the technical activities between WPs were carried out successfully in a coordinated manner, the services from the technical WPs have been successfully integrated or have defined a roadmap for that, the services were successfully onboarded in the EOSC marketplace and integrated with various other EOSC services.</p> <p>Similarly, the SC in collaboration with the PC, have been actively monitoring the impact of initial results in scientific communities, trying to identify synergies and interdisciplinarity collaborations, and recommend strategies to engage other communities leveraging the EOSC ecosystem and expanding the current user base of researchers. As a result, multiple meetings have taken place during the second half of this period with the scientific communities to get feedback and discuss the impact of initial results in their communities, and additionally, multiple actions have been carried out in different EOSC activities to contribute to and leverage the ecosystem.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● technical activities between WPs were carried out successfully in a coordinated manner ● the services from the technical WPs have been successfully integrated or are working based on a clear roadmap in this direction ● the services were successfully onboarded in the EOSC marketplace and integrated with various other EOSC services ● multiple meetings have taken place during the second half of this period with the scientific communities to get feedback and discuss the impact of initial results in their communities ● Active participation and support of different EOSC activities in order to leverage the ecosystem, influence its shaping and promote RELIANCE results with the end goal of expanding the RELIANCE user base. Some of these actions include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ collaboration with EOSC Future and other InfraEOSC07 projects in different areas including technical activities, uptake (open calls) and training, formalised in a collaboration agreement also accepted by the EC. ○ supporting EOSC future demo to EC with a compelling use case leveraging initial version of RELIANCE services 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ involvement in the semantic interoperability task force (TF), which is co-led by the RELIANCE SC, with representatives in the TF themes (metadata standards, catalogues, and use cases) ○ involvement in the Research Product Publishing Framework WG ○ involvement in the Compute Continuum WG ○ supporting the technical alignment with EOSC science projects ○ contributing to the EOSC Multiannual Roadmap (MAR) 2023-2024
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested
No risks or deviations have been detected during this period.
Next Steps in Next Period
In the next period this task will continue monitoring the impact of results in scientific communities and being active actors in the different EOSC activities, to contribute to its shaping, promote RELIANCE results and leverage existing communities to extend RELIANCE user base. This includes continuing the activities in the TF and WG already identified (Semantic Interoperability, Research Product Publishing Framework, Compute Continuum). Similarly this task will continue to monitor all general technical aspects in the project, ensuring that all technical milestones are met, and in particular monitoring updates in the EOSC ecosystem that could impact the RELIANCE services.

3.1.1 Task 1.3

Task	Title
1.3	Management of IPR, Ethics and legal issues
Contributors	PSNC, all
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project, task 1.3 has focused on the analysis and initial specification of the strategy for IPR management, including the definition of basic principles, main IPR actions and exploitable results. This task has been acting supported by and in alignment with the work in WP2 regarding the exploitation strategy and business plan, and taking into account the principles set in the Grant Agreement (GA) and in the Consortium Agreement (CA). The basic principles in RELIANCE IPR strategy include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The RELIANCE project is committed to providing free open access to new research data resulting from the project (one of H2020's main objectives). ● All scientific activities based on research objects technologies are openly available in alignment with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles. ● IPR will maintain a schedule of innovation during the course of the project and explore the opportunities for applying for patents or declaring copyrights for results, e.g., for the services and other exploitable results. This will be analysed more in detail in the second period. <p>Moreover, the general principles for exploitable results include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ownership of results belongs solely to the beneficiary that generates them (in full agreement of the GA and CA) ● Joint ownership by several beneficiaries comes into action in case results have been jointly generated by two or more beneficiaries and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection rights. ● Background was clearly identified within the CA, which was concluded among the partners before the GA was signed. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access rights to the beneficiaries will give each other access to the background needed to implement their own tasks under the action. <p>Additionally, this task has monitored the project activities for any ethical or legal issues, although none appeared during this period.</p>
Significant Results during the Year 1
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis and initial specification of the strategy for IPR management, including the definition of basic principles and exploitable results. monitoring for any ethical or legal issue that may appear in the project
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested
<p>No risks or deviations have been detected during this period.</p>
Next Steps in Next Period
<p>In the next period this task will define more in detail the IPR management strategy, as the first version of the services has been released, onboarded in EOSC and integrated with other EOSC services. Also this task will continue to monitor for any ethical or legal issue that may appear in the project.</p>

3.1.1 Task 1.4

Task	Title
1.4	Quality Assurance, Risk, Data and Innovation Management
Contributors	PSNC, all
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project, task 1.4 has managed the project quality processes, including monitoring the project milestones and KPIs, the compliance of the management structure, and that deliverables and internal reports are submitted in due time and following the review process. The deliverable review process, described in D1.1, assigns a reviewer (different from the author(s)) to each deliverable, and provides the recommended schedule for executing the review. Similarly, this task monitored the identified risks in order to be able to take prompt actions if it were deemed necessary.</p> <p>Moreover, as part of this task, an external advisory board was created. They were provided with all the documents of the projects in order to provide recommendations/feedback regarding the work carried out in the project. One dedicated meeting between the EAB and the RELIANCE took place in September last year.</p> <p>This task also delivered the initial project Data Management Plan (DMP) (D1.2), which addresses the relevant aspects of making data FAIR, as part of RELIANCE commitment to the Open Research Data (ORD) Pilot. The DMP was also implemented and made available via the EOSC service called Argos.</p> <p>Finally, this task coordinated the project activities to pave the way for innovation and exploitation/uptake, tightly interrelated with the networking, exploitation and business planning activities. In this period the activities were centred in facilitating the dialogue between the different user communities – Sea Monitoring, Climate Monitoring, GeoHazard – and the different partners responsible for the technical development. This prepared a common ground for the second year when the scientific partners will be asked to be the main services ambassadors in terms of training and penetration into new potential communities of users. Additionally, different actions were carried out to start a dialogue with external communities of early adopters within and outside Europe.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	

<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specification of the quality review process for deliverables (part of D1.1) • D1.2 Initial Data Management Plan (DMP) • Implementation of DMP in EOSC service called Argos https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/publicOverview/24a939db-f8fc-4864-bce9-924ea4887c17 • Monitoring of the project quality processes and risks • Creation of an External Advisory Board and organisation of a dedicated meeting event • Coordination of the innovation management.
<p>Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested</p> <p>No risks or deviations have been detected during this period.</p>
<p>Next Steps in Next Period</p> <p>In the next period this task will maintain and update as necessary the project DMP, and will continue the monitoring of the project quality processes and risks. Similarly, in the next period, with all services operational and onboarded in EOSC, this task will continue and boost the management of innovation and exploitation/uptake.</p>

3.2 WP2 – Outreach exploitation and capacity building

During these months many activities have been set up to carry out the activities foreseen within WP2. Dissemination and communication activities were laid out and set up since the very beginning of the project. These means support the exploitation activity. In this period, an overview of existing materials useful for the exploitation activity was performed together with the identification of effective strategies that are better fit for the scope and the ambitious aims of the project. Clustering activities with sister projects were carried out, including liaising with other projects in the INFRAEOSC-07, looking for synergies and collaborations of activities. Additionally, engagements with relevant key actors and stakeholders to foster the uptake of RELIANCE services have been carried out paving the way for RELIANCE Challenge (Open Call) and encouraging the exploitation of RELIANCE in several domains. A list of RELIANCE presentations and presence at events and other dissemination activities is provided in detail in D2.4.

3.2.1 Task 2.1

Task	Title
2.1	Exploitation Strategy & Business Plan under the EOSC framework
Contributors	ALPHA; All.
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project several activities have been performed i.e. validation of findings (coming from previous projects and desk analysis); preliminary RELIANCE business models and BP methodologies. Hence, the preparation of new analysis and materials followed. At this stage, the Issue 1 of 2.1 “Business plan & exploitation strategy - Issue 1” was delivered in M12.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of Issue 1 of D2.1 in M12 – The output of this deliverable will be reviewed and validated with key partners and stakeholders, in view of the second issue of the deliverable. 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	
N/A	

Next Steps in Next Period

The next steps foreseen in the Task include the follow-up of the RELIANCE exploitation in place activities in view of the Issue 2 of D2.1, in order to further finetune the outcomes of the “Business Plan and exploitation strategy - Issue 1” deliverable (submitted in M13).

3.2.1 Task 2.2

Task	Title
2.2	Dissemination, Communication, networking & exchange
Contributors	T2, CNR, INGV, UiO
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project: the D2.3 “Dissemination and communication plan” was delivered in M2 and D2.4 was delivered at the end of M12. D2.3 is reviewed/updated on a regular basis, and sets the guideline for promotion activities carried out by the consortium, including scouting of relevant conferences, workshops, events and journals aligned with the project scopes. At the same time D2.4 provided the description of communication materials collected during Year 1 as well as all the conferences and meetings attended by consortium partners to promote RELIANCE. A second version of D2.4 is foreseen at M24.</p> <p>Collaborations with INFRAEOSC-07 project stack are ongoing on a regular basis: this enables to increase awareness on RELIANCE services and extend the uptake to other communities that may be involved in the different projects.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.3 “Dissemination and communication plan” • D2.4 “Report on Communication Materials” • Project website fully functional - 1K visitors during the first year • Social media channels setup and consolidation (around 50 followers on Twitter mainly from twin projects within the infra EOSC 7 ecosystem) • Videos on RELIANCE services – 3 info animations describing the project, the services and the opportunities to interact with the project. 100 views on Youtube, 900views on Twitter. • Video Pills project – creation of a video production system to allow scientific partners to quickly explain services and their value on the job – to be used for training activities in Year 2. On going 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	
Dissemination and communication activities develop in parallel with the maturity and stability of RELIANCE services, which are delivered at M12. Core communication activities foreseen during the second year of the project.	
Next Steps in Next Period	
<p>Cluster activities with the INFRAEOSC-07 project stack in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From Jan 22 – Ask me anything session to widen the community of users – to be integrated with our seminars. https://eoscc-portal.eu/services-resources to be used as the standard to describe services to users • Hackathon for service usage in April and May 2022. <p>Other activities are envisaged in view of the promotional activities of the RELIANCE Challenge and T2.3 activities (when needed).</p>	

3.2.1 Task 2.3

Task	Title
2.3	Epistemic communities' engagement & capacity building
Contributors	ALPHA, All.
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project, ALPHA worked on co-developing the three info animations for epistemic communities' early adopters. This represents the step 1 of a more comprehensive strategy focused on building the basic communication tools that came to light in summer 2021. The networking activities were focused on involving in house RELIANCE scientists pertaining to 3 main virtual research communities: The Sea Monitoring: CNR ISMAR; The Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratories: INGV; The Atmospheric and Climate modelling: University of Oslo.</p> <p>The efforts were expanded to third research organisations/networks/Institutions in horizontal use-case scenarios applied to the grand challenge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grand Challenge 1: Sea pollution • Grand Challenge 2: Loss of Biodiversity and Sustainability (Biodiversity, fisheries, marine litter) • Grand Challenge 3: Extreme weather events and climate adaptation (biomass) • Grand Challenge 4: Reducing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions <p>The team set in place a strategic road map for engagement of user communities extending to relevant actors and stakeholders, unfolded in 5 steps:</p> <p>STEP 1. Building the communication basis (info animations) (M9):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The added value of EOSC for researchers; • The RELIANCE services; • The RELIANCE early adopters' engagement. <p>STEP 2. Preparing pre-service video-intros (M11-13):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video Pills on each service by RELIANCE researchers (general and promotional); • Show practical examples (Tutorials); • Story telling by RELIANCE testimonials introducing the added value of RELIANCE services to the broad scientific communities. <p>STEP 3. Preliminary contact with early adopters (M11-14):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare the ToR of the RELIANCE challenge (M11); • Prepare the application form online of the call with dedicated e-mail account or web-based submission for applicants (M12); • Introduce early adopters to the RELIANCE-EOSC services (formal letter plus info animations link) and invitation to join brainstorming sessions (M13/M14); • Setting up initial brainstorming with clusters of early adopters' research centres, universities and other institutions on RELIANCE services and the challenge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three cluster meeting have been carried out so far (one in December, one in January, one in February), and one is scheduled for the end of February <p>STEP 4. Preparing tutorials/coaching on RELIANCE services use (M14)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video Pills on services by ES Community (specific and instructive); • Service guidelines to users; • Web meetings between RELIANCE testimonials and clusters of early adopters with interactive sessions. 	

STEP 5. Execution phase (M15-):

- Preparation of a webinar (workshop on line) devoted to present: concept, tools, grand challenges, standards of application and coaching services of the challenge to the selected institutions and affiliated researchers (M13-15);
- Execution of webinar (workshop on line – info days) and call opening (M15);
- Organise webinars (once every 2 months) to coach and monitor the use of the services

Significant Results during the Year 1

Besides having set out and proceeded with the implementation of the five step roadmap of the task we also achieved the following:

- implemented the first horizontal brainstorming meeting on RELIANCE services for early adopters on Dec. 22nd;
- Involve the UNESCO Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), to foster the early adoption of RELIANCE services as well as increased awareness across several user communities;
- Involve the Division of Science Policy and capacity building of UNESCO HQ

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

A shift of Deliverable D2.7 “Report on Epistemic Communities Networking and Cooperation – Issue 1”, was requested from month 12 to month 14 along with the RELIANCE Challenge shifted from month 10 to month 15. The reasons for that are mainly connected with the activities related to preparation of the EOSC Future INFRAEOSC07 projects Multi-lateral Collaboration Agreement, and the alignment of RELIANCE with the EOSC Future & INFRAEOSC-07-2020 projects collaboration topics. In particular, regarding the topics of uptake and training, which include among others:

- Production of 1 page document summarizing the benefits of becoming an EOSC service and content provider (Spring 2022)
- Production of 1 page document summarizing how to become an EOSC service and content provider (Spring 2022)
- Creation of catchy communication and promotional material (Spring 2022)
- “Ask me anything” sessions, bi-monthly to present the EOSC services and widen the EOSC user base.
- EOSC Future provider days (April 2022, May 2023)
- EOSC Hackathon (fall 2022)
- A series of joint training activities (2 per year)

Additionally, the introduction of the services to early adopters’ communities required additional alphabetization efforts beyond the technical dimension of the project. Based on that, we modified slightly the approach of our challenge and started making preparation activities before we actually launch the challenge. The challenge itself will be then launched in Spring 2022 (instead of M10) in alignment with most of the collaboration activities mentioned above. However, we already started with the preparation activities, as described above.

Next Steps in Next Period

Follow-up of foreseen activities for the RELIANCE challenge, in view also of the above mentioned deviations. In particular:

- Finalization of the RELIANCE services user guidelines (M13-M14);
- Preparation of vertical and horizontal brainstorming webinars for early adopters (workshop online) devoted to present: concept, tools, grand challenges, standards of

application and coaching services of the RELIANCE challenge to the selected institutions and affiliated researchers (at least 3 prior to the call M12-15)

- Execution of webinar (workshop on line – info days) and call opening (M15);
- Organise webinars (upon necessity) to coach and monitor the use of the RELIANCE services

The outcomes of the CHALLENGE will be presented at the final event of RELIANCE “European Open Science Cloud in advanced data-driven research for sustainable development” (M24).

3.3 WP3 – Mining and enrichment of scientific text

The work in WP3 has been carried out as expected according to the plan, without any major deviation. During the first four months the main effort was focused on T3.1 to identify, gather, and leverage the resources necessary to customize the text mining tools to the scientific vocabulary used by the user communities in RELIANCE. As a result, we produced a text corpus of scientific documents in the domains of interest for RELIANCE users and analysed the corpus to improve the knowledge graph used by the text mining tools. We also studied the OpenAIRE knowledge graph as a relevant source of scientific publications that is useful to enhance the results of some of the tools developed in the project, such as the recommendation engine.

Based on the customised knowledge graph resulting from T3.1, our work in T3.2 focused on developing the services to enrich research objects and single documents with semantic metadata. To enhance the semantic metadata beyond lemmas, concepts, entities, and topics we also fine-tuned a neural language model to categorize documents and research objects against a taxonomy of fields of research. The field of research classifier is ongoing work that we plan to finish in the second stage of the project. We integrated the semantic enrichment services in ROHub and onboarded them into EOSC as standalone services, covering both document-level and research object-level enrichment needs. In task T3.3, we developed a search engine that allows users to search research objects exploiting the semantic metadata previously generated by the enrichment service.

In T3.3, we also developed a recommendation system that leverages such metadata to suggest possible research objects of interest related to the content of a selection of other research objects. The search engine and the recommendation system have also been deployed in ROHub and onboarded into EOSC. Finally, the work on T3.4 is in its initial stage since this task relies on the previous tasks and main developments are planned for the second half of the project. We have already identified key resources and state-of-the art models that will serve as a basis for the services that we will develop in this task during the next reporting period. During the next period, we will also refine and evolve the results of tasks T3.2 and T3.3.

3.3.1 Task 3.1

Task	Title
3.1	Terminology analysis and resource customization
Contributors	ESI, UPM, PSNC, MEEO
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
During the first year of the project, we worked on the preparation of the necessary resources to customize the text mining tools to the scientific vocabulary of RELIANCE user communities. We carry out a survey with the user communities to identify the fields of research where they usually work. Then, we harvested from the knowledge graph of scientific publications SN SciGraph a corpus of papers published in the last 5 years that belongs to these fields of research. This text corpus is used in RELIANCE to enhance the coverage of the scientific domain vocabulary in the text mining services and during the project will be used to learn new models or fine-tune pre-trained models to tackle the more experimental text mining services such as reading comprehension. We	

analysed the text in this corpus using a general-purpose text mining tool and identified concepts and entities not currently covered. Such unknown concepts and entities are analysed by linguistics who integrate them in Sensigrafo. Sensigrafo is the knowledge graph of linguistic information underlying the RELIANCE text mining and enrichment services. As a result of the aforementioned process, the text mining and enrichment services have now been enabled to understand the domain terminology used by the scientific communities of interest in the project.

In this task, we also explored other resources that the text mining services can exploit in RELIANCE. We focus on the OpenAIRE repository, which interlinks scientific outputs including papers, data, and software across different repositories. Text mining services, including the search and recommendation engines, will leverage research objects in ROHub and scientific outputs in OpenAIRE to offer a more complete set of scientific resources. We also reviewed the OpenAIRE Open Citation initiative, which makes available the citation graph of research works that we plan to leverage to generate the influence network of research.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- A text corpus and terminology relevant for the Earth Science communities.
- A customized and extended version of the Sensigrafo knowledge graph based on such resources.
- We released in Zenodo the RELIANCE text corpus and the domain terminology that we identified: https://zenodo.org/record/4721343/files/reliance_weirdness_filtered.json
- Deliverable D3.1 Semantic Resources was delivered as planned.

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

None

Next Steps in Next Period

This task was foresighted from M1 to M4 and its status is finished. No further steps planned.

3.3.2 Task 3.2

Task	Title
3.2	Information extraction and semantic annotation
Contributors	ESI, UPM, PSNC, MEE0
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>We have developed a text mining service to enrich single documents and research objects with semantic metadata describing their content. This text analytic service relies on the version of the Sensigrafo knowledge graph customized to the scientific vocabulary used by RELIANCE communities that was produced as part of task T3.1. The goal of the enrichment service is to generate a synthesis of the research object or the single document by identifying the most relevant concepts, lemmas, named entities and topics mentioned in the content. Lemmas are the actual terms used to refer to concepts including morphological variations and synonyms. Concepts identify groups of words sharing a meaning that are explicitly modelled in the Sensigrafo. Named entities are mentions of people, localizations, and organizations. Topics represent the high-level matters dealt with in the text.</p> <p>In addition, we are working on improving the enrichment service to provide Field of Research metadata based on the content of the documents and research objects analysed. Fields of research</p>	

are scientific categories arranged in the ANZSRC taxonomy¹. To generate this type of metadata, we trained a classifier by fine-tuning a pre-trained language model² using the SciGraph text corpus gathered in T3.1, where scientific papers are tagged with Field of Research categories. Currently we have a first version of the Field of Research classifier as a stand-alone service. In the second phase of the project, we plan to integrate this classifier in the enrichment service.

In the single document mode, the enrichment service can process text from pdf, docx and ppt files. In the future, we also plan to support other formats, like text contained in markdown documents and jupyter notebooks. When the input is a research object the service extracts the text from the pdf docx, and ppt files in the research object and then analyse the aggregated text.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- Enrichment service for research objects integrated in ROHub latest version. Every public research object in ROHub is enriched with semantic metadata describing its content
- Enrichment service for documents integrated in EOSC.
- Customization of the enrichment service to the scientific vocabulary used by RELIANCE user communities
- A first version of a classifier that assigns Fields of Research to documents.

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

None

Next Steps in Next Period

The Field of Research classifier and its integration in the enrichment service is an on-going process. More experiments will be carried out in the next period to train more classifiers increasing the accuracy and other evaluation metrics.

In the next period we plan to work on extracting structural metadata such as title, abstract, authors, tables or figures and citations from scientific papers encapsulated in research objects. Once Data cubes references (links) are agreed and used by the RELIANCE user communities, we also plan to extract these references from publications, as well as other documents, and make them part of the metadata generated by the enrichment service.

Finally, we also plan to develop several demonstrators to convey the utility of the enrichment services to the RELIANCE and EOSC scientific communities. Such demonstrators include i) a web application that given a piece of text allows the user to explore the metadata extracted from it by the enrichment service and ii) a browser plugin that allows scientists to ingest scientific publications into their bibliographic research objects as they browse the internet searching for relevant literature for their research. Both will be available from the landing page of the enrichment services in EOSC.

3.3.3 Task 3.3

Task	Title
3.3	Content-based retrieval and recommendation
Contributors	ESI, UPM, PSNC, MEE0
Summary of Progress during Year 1	

1 Taxonomy available at: <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/classifications/australian-and-new-zealand-standard-research-classification-anzsrc/latest-release>

2 In the Field of research classifier, we use RoBERTa: <https://ai.facebook.com/blog/roberta-an-optimized-method-for-pretraining-self-supervised-nlp-systems/>

We have developed the first versions of a search engine and a recommendation engine of research objects. The search engine supports both keyword-based and faceted search. The facets include all the metadata generated by the enrichment service for research objects developed in task 3.2. Such metadata includes lemmas, concepts, entities, topics, and fields of research. The search engine leverages that information to enable users to retrieve research objects more precisely and easily. The recommendation engine suggests potentially relevant research objects based on the content of a selection of other research objects or users. If the reference is a research object, the recommendation engine uses the semantic metadata of the research object to recommend similar research objects. If the reference is a user, the recommendation engine first aggregates all the semantic metadata of the research objects owned by such user and then uses the semantic metadata to suggest relevant research objects. When both research objects and users are used as reference in the recommendation context the system aggregates all the semantic metadata from the research object and the user's research objects to suggest similar research objects based on the aggregated metadata.

In addition, we worked on the graphical user interface of the recommendation engine called Collaboration Spheres. In this web application, users can use a drag and drop interface to explore the ROHub research object collection. Currently the system is limited to use as reference for the recommendation of public research objects. The Collaboration Spheres are ongoing work.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- Search service for research objects deployed and integrated in ROHub and the onboarding into EOSC has been approved.
- Recommendation service for research objects deployed and integrated in ROHub and the onboarding into EOSC has been approved.

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

None

Next Steps in Next Period

In the next period, we plan to deploy a user interface for the search service. The search engine user interface is planned in the shape of a dashboard where users can query using keywords and facets using traditional query boxes and widgets for the different facets.

For the Collaboration Spheres we will finish the integration with the new ROHub authentication mechanism. This will enable the use of ROHub users as the recommendation reference.

Finally, we will explore the OpenAIRE knowledge graph and corresponding API to integrate part of the information which is relevant for the RELIANCE communities in the recommendation system. Thus, the recommendation system can suggest research objects and papers in OpenAIRE.

3.3.4 Task 3.4

Task	Title
3.4	Extended analytics services in support of the scientific enterprise
Contributors	ESI, UPM, PSNC, MEEO
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
As stated in the Grant Agreement, T3.4 activities build upon the services developed in T3.2 and T3.3. During the first year we have been putting in place all the required services to start working on the second period on the following services that are proposed in T3.4: Influence network extraction (how different pieces of research and their corresponding publications influence each other, based on the content of their associated research objects), Novelty Score (how innovative is	

a research work judging by the content of its corresponding research objects and publications), Support to Reading Comprehension, and Text Mining and Enrichment Dashboard.

We have identified OpenAIRE as a key resource for the activities in this task. The peer-reviewed publications in OpenAIRE can be used as reference of existing work to calculate the Novelty Score for a given research object. In addition, from these publications and the OpenAIRE knowledge graph we can extract the network of authors, papers, and citations to build the influence network.

For the reading comprehension task, we have reviewed the state of the art on machine reading comprehension and question answering, as well as question generation. The state of the art on these tasks is achieved by fine-tuning language models like RoBERTa on a question answering dataset containing paragraphs, questions, and answers. We plan to use a question generation model to generate questions from a research object text, and a question answering model to extract the answer for the generated question from the text.

Finally, for the text mining and enrichment dashboard we have identified Kibana as the technology to develop the dashboard. This software allows building dashboards with different widgets based on documents indexed in Elasticsearch. We plan to index the research objects in such index and visualize the semantic metadata using the dashboard.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- Identification of OpenAIRE knowledge graph as a key resource for the Novelty Score calculation and the extraction of the influence network.
- Identification of state-of-the-art models for machine reading comprehension.
- Identification of the technology stack for the dashboard deployment.

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

None

Next Steps in Next Period

In the next period we plan to implement:

- The novelty score calculation and including it as part of the metadata produced by the enrichment service.
- The extraction of the influence network using information from ROHub and OpenAIRE
- The support for machine reading comprehension using neural language models to generate questions in the form of quizzes that facilitate and evaluate understanding, as well as the answers to such questions for paragraphs in scientific documents.
- The text mining and enrichment dashboard using Kibana to visualize all the semantic metadata added to user's research objects.

3.4 WP4 – FAIR Data Cube s for multi-dimensional research data access & reuse

In the reporting period M01-M12, the WP4 focused on setting up and onboarding to the European Open Science Cloud the FAIR data cube services to exploit Copernicus and geospatial products identified by RELIANCE user communities.

This work package consists of four tasks described in the following sections.

3.4.1 Task 4.1

Task	Title
4.1	Data Cube metadata model

Contributors	UPM (Leader), PSNC, MEE0
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the early stage of the project, the overall RELIANCE consortium engaged with the definition of the data cube metadata model. The leader of the task organised a series of bilateral and whole consortium discussions to collect relevant metadata schemas adopted by user communities, standards and best practices adopted by technical partners to come out with the deliverable D4.1 - Data Cube metadata model.</p> <p>This task also supported the alignment with other metadata related activities within EOSC to improve the level of interoperability of data cube services with EOSC services.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of relevant metadata schemas adopted by RELIANCE user communities • D4.1 - Data Cube metadata model. 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	
No major risks have been detected during this period.	
Next Steps in Next Period	
None.	

3.4.2 Task 4.2

Task	Title
4.2	Data Cubes connection to research objects
Contributors	MEE0 (Leader) UPM, PSNC
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project this task focused on the analysis of different integration scenarios of data cube and research objects: among the different scenarios, the first release of integration focused more on the support of functional requirements rather than on effective integration (i.e., support of integration by reference) of data cube resources.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.2 – Data Cube API. First release of the API package with a preliminary set of functionalities to discover, explore, access FAIR data cubes. • Jupyter Notebook examples to showcase how to exploit data cube resources and research object services • Demonstration to RELIANCE user communities of data cube services 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	
No major risks have been detected during this period.	
Next Steps in Next Period	
<p>In the next period this task will continue with the “integration by reference” of data cube resources into research objects. The potential of the integration has demonstrated the added value to improve the FAIRness level of the RELIANCE services, but to avoid data duplication it has been planned to evolve the data cube API to support the access via URI.</p>	

3.4.3 Task 4.3

Task	Title
4.3	Data Cubes customization, extensions
Contributors	MEE0 (Leader), UPM, PSNC

<p>Summary of Progress during Year 1</p> <p>During the first year of the project this task focused on evolving and customising the ADAM platform to support the data cube metadata model according to Task 4.1. Among the key functionalities and OGC standard services already supported, the customization and extensions needed to manage the variety of Copernicus and geospatial data products identified by RELIANCE user communities have been identified and planned for implementation.</p> <p>Taking advantage of the involvement of MEO in the OGC Testbed-17 initiative, the alignment with OGC Geo data cube definition and conceptual model were also taken in consideration.</p>
<p>Significant Results during the Year 1</p> <p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of the data cube metadata model • Customization of OpenSearch and Web Coverage Service (WCS) to support RELIANCE data cubes
<p>Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested</p> <p>No major risks have been detected during this period.</p>
<p>Next Steps in Next Period</p> <p>For the next period this task will continue the customization and extensions of data cube services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support of data cube via HTTPS and S3 protocols • To manage different data profiles (e.g. satellite-based, model-based, in-situ) • To manage heterogeneous temporal and spatial resolution • To enable data cube processing services (e.g. average, min, max, ...) • Alignment with OGC Testbed-17 conceptual model

3.4.4 Task 4.4

Task	Title
4.4	Data Cube setup and population
Contributors	MEO (Leader), UPM, PSNC
<p>Summary of Progress during Year 1</p> <p>During the first year of the project, within this task the following activities have been handled: provisioning of cloud resources for the development and production environments at MEO infrastructure, setup up of RELIANCE data cube services, and population (collection, processing and indexing) of Copernicus and geospatial data products.</p>	
<p>Significant Results during the Year 1</p> <p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.3 –FAIR Data Cubes. • The deployment and operation of the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform for the management of data cubes, including a development instance and a production instance • Collection of user data cube requirements • The deployment and hosting of 20+ data cubes for RELIANCE communities 	
<p>Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested</p> <p>No major risks have been detected during this period.</p>	
<p>Next Steps in Next Period</p> <p>For the next period this task will continue the data cube population both to integrate new geospatial data products and to extend the spatial and temporal coverage of already supported Copernicus and geospatial data products.</p>	

3.5 WP5 – FAIR Research Objects for the management of the scientific lifecycle in EOSC

During the first 12 months of the project WP5 focused on adapting and extending research object services for the management of the scientific lifecycle in EOSC. This included

- the analysis of EOSC metadata guidelines and recommendations, the research object models, the data cube metadata model described in WP4, as well as the needs of user communities and stakeholders to describe scientific information in their communities in order to define an RO model adapted to EOSC. As a result, an RO-crate profile for RELIANCE was produced for describing research objects in EOSC.
- the analysis of existing approaches for assessing the FAIR-ness of research artefacts, such as data and software, and the initial approaches/challenges towards the assessment of research objects as a single information unit.
- the extension, adaptation and deployment of a RELIANCE checklist service for the evaluation of the research quality following a community driven approach, including the implementation of an initial set of checklists, as well as the initial adaptation of existing stability service to monitor the research object quality over time.
- the extension of the mechanisms supporting the versioning and evolution of research objects, allowing composite lifecycle workflows and the connection with relevant EOSC services to deposit releases of research objects in an automatic manner. This also included supporting the RO-crate specification for transferring research objects.
- the integration of the latest enrichment service (WP3) in ROHub, the extension of ROHub to support RELIANCE vocabulary allowing the aggregation of data cubes (WP4) in research objects, and the provision of functional user interfaces to access research object functionalities, including a python API library and an updated reference Web portal.

3.5.1 Task 5.1 – RO model alignment with metadata guidelines and EOSC recommendations

Task	Title
5.1	RO model alignment with metadata guidelines and EOSC recommendations
Contributors	UPM, PSNC, ESI
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project, this task carried out the activities necessary to deliver the RO specification to be used in RELIANCE for the representation of research objects. These included the analysis of existing specifications for the representation of research objects and the definition of metadata models for the research artefacts aggregated in ROs taking into account EOSC and related metadata guidelines (e.g., OpenAire, Datacite) and the data cube metadata model described in D4.1. Based on that work, this task provided the specification of the RELIANCE RO-crate profile, which extends the RO-crate specification to represent data cube centric research objects. This work was described in deliverable D5.1 - RO model adapted to EOSC. More details about the profile implementation, which included the development of the RELIANCE vocabulary extending RO-crate (based on schema.org) with the terms to describe data cubes (D4.1), was described in D5.2 - Design, Implementation and deployment of research object services.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.1 “RO model adapted to EOSC” • Vocabulary: https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/ro-terms/blob/master/earth-science/vocabulary.ttl • RELIANCE RO-Crate profile: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/reliance-ro-crate/ 	

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested
<p>The analysis to be done on the different metadata catalogues and standards used across domains took more time than expected, due to the discussions held with the user communities that led to the identification of more metadata catalogues and standards than originally planned.</p> <p>There was a delayed in D5.1 due to factors: i) the delay on D4.1 DataCube Data Model, a reference document for this deliverable, and ii) the task required a deeper analysis of the adaptations required to extend the RO model (RO-Crate) with the specificities of the data cubes to be represented.</p>
Next Steps in Next Period
<p>This task ended at M6 although new terms could be incorporated in the future to the vocabulary during the project.</p>

3.5.2 Task 5.2 – Guidelines and tools for self-assessment of FAIR research object compliance

Task	Title
5.2	Guidelines and tools for self-assessment of FAIR research object compliance
Contributors	UPM, PSNC, ESI
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project, the activities have been related with the deliverable D5.2 “Design, Implementation and deployment of research object services”. Guidelines to assess the FAIRness of data and software have been identified, as well as metrics. A lack of guidelines to assess the FAIRness of a RO (as a whole) have not been identified, which will be our priority to create this guideline for the next period.</p> <p>A set of tools such as F-UJI, HowFairs, SOMEF and FOOPS were identified as potential tools to be integrated in our system. After this analysis, it has been decided to start the work of integration with the tool F-UJI.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.2 “Design, Implementation and deployment of research object services” 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	
<p>No major risks have been detected during this period. A potential risk for the second period will be the integration of F-UJI service into our system. For it, we will start the work with this component to have time in case an integration problem arises.</p>	
Next Steps in Next Period	
<p>During the second year of the project, this task will deploy a service to assess the FAIRness of research objects based on RO-Crate. This service will not only take into account the metadata of the RO, but also the metadata of the resources aggregated to the RO.</p>	

3.5.3 Task 5.3 – Community driven quality evaluation and curation

Task	Title
5.3	Community driven quality evaluation and curation
Contributors	PSNC, UPM, ESI
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project different activities were carried out to provide the mechanisms and tools to support the assessment of research objects quality according to what the research</p>	

communities producing and reusing them consider relevant, including metrics as accuracy, completeness, or availability. This task has extended and adapted existing research object quality assessment technology based on checklists that define a list of requirements that must be fulfilled or assessed for a given task. This included the adaptation of the checklist service to interact efficiently with the latest ROHub (research object management) platform, as well as its extension to support RELIANCE metadata models and vocabularies (aligned with EOSC). Similarly, this task has adapted the existing service (aka. stability service) to monitor the quality over time in order to use the latest version of checklist service, and to integrate it with ROHub. Additionally, new checklists have been created to reflect the current RELIANCE community's needs.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- D5.2 "Design, Implementation and deployment of research object services"
- RELIANCE version of checklist service adapted and extended to interact with ROHub and to support RELIANCE metadata models and vocabularies (aligned with EOSC)
- RELIANCE version of stability service adapted to latest changes in checklist service
- Initial set of checklists reflecting the RELIANCE community's needs.

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

No risks or deviations have been detected during this period.

Next Steps in Next Period

In the next period, this task will provide additional checklists reflecting the RELIANCE community's needs, and integrate the stability service with ROHub. Additionally, this task aims at providing mechanisms enabling an easy customization of checklists to community needs, as well as providing appropriate interfaces not only to assess but also to correct/improve the quality of the research object in a user-friendly manner.

3.5.4 Task 5.4 – Versioning and Evolution

Task	Title
5.4	Versioning and evolution
Contributors	PSNC, UPM, ESI
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project this task extended the research lifecycle support mechanisms in ROHub in order to leverage and reuse existing EOSC services. Accordingly, research objects snapshots/archives can now be published in general/popular EOSC repositories like Zenodo or B2Share. This integration aims to contribute to the ROs dissemination, increasing their findability and potential reuse (i.e., their FAIRness). For this task, ROHub was extended to support the latest RO-crate specification, which is the standard method to capture and describe the research object with structured metadata (see D5.1). RO-crate is the format used to deposit the ROs in those repositories. This functionality has been made available via the user interfaces, i.e., the ROHub portal and the ROHub python library.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D5.2 "Design, Implementation and deployment of research object services" ● Support of RO-crate specification in ROHub. ● Possibility to export research objects as RO-Crates in ROHub ● Integration of Zenodo and B2Share in ROHub in collaboration with WP6 ● Extension of lifecycle in ROHub to support the publication of research objects in Zenodo/B2share. 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	

No risks or deviations have been detected during this period.

Next Steps in Next Period

In the next period, the following tasks are expected:

- Integration of ROHub with additional EOSC services, in particular B2Drop, which the user will be able to choose as the default storage location for the internal resources added and aggregated by the research object during its lifecycle.
- To analyse feasibility and potentially support additional operations during the research life cycle, such as the merging and/or creation of pull requests from research object forks to their source research object, or to support additional repositories for publishing research objects snapshots, such as GitHub.

3.5.5 Task 5.5 – Integration and access

Task	Title
5.5	Integration and access
Contributors	PSNC, UPM, ESI
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project this task worked on the integration of results from WP3 and WP4 in ROHub to allow automatic enrichment of research objects, and the aggregation of data cubes and their description in research objects. Additionally, this task provided the first version of user interfaces to access research objects functionalities, including a new and enhanced Web portal and a python API library to access the research objects services from Jupyter notebooks and other environments. This includes also the release of the user documentation for the portal and for the library.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D5.2 “Design, Implementation and deployment of research object services” ● Release of fully functional ROHub API library: https://git.man.poznan.pl/stash/projects/ROHUB/repos/rohub-api/browse ● Release of new and improved ROHub Web portal: http://reliance.rohub.org/ ● Rich documentation of ROHub API library: - https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/index.html, and an initial version of portal documentation: https://reliance-eosc.github.io/rohub-portal-documentation/ ● Integration with latest version of enrichment service from WP3 ● Support of RELIANCE vocabulary (D5.1) in ROHub to allow the aggregation of data cubes in research objects ● First Ask Me Anything Session of ROHub with RELIANCE research communities 	
Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested	
No risks or deviations have been detected during this period.	
Next Steps in Next Period	
<p>In the next period, the following tasks are expected:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improvements in the ROHub API library based on the users’ feedback ● Improvements in the ROHub Web portal based on the users’ feedback ● Improvement of user documentation, including tutorials ● Integration of WP3 dashboards and additional services in ROHub user interfaces 	

- Tighter integration with data cubes services to support more efficient reuse, including the loading of data cubes in WP4 services from ROHub for their reuse and visualisation, or customised interfaces to aggregate and describe data cubes in research objects.

3.6 WP6 – EOSC Integration and Service Offering

During the first 12 months of the project, WP6 focused its activities in making available the project services through the EOSC delivery channels. It included activities for the technical service provisioning and helpdesk activities. The services being integrated through the EOSC delivery channels are:

- Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities, which relies upon ROHub platform as the reference service;
- Data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access, with the integration of the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform through the EOSC delivery channels;
- Text mining and semantic enrichment services to allow extracting machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research, and which rely on expert.ai’s AI-based NLP/U platform as base system.
- Copernicus Earth Observation Data Pipelines to provide an integrated intermediate service layer for the systematic execution of Earth Observation Applications continuously delivering data and information to users.

3.6.1 Task 6.1

Task	Title
6.1	EOSC Integration
Contributors	PSNC, Terradue, MEEO, ESI
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project different activities were carried out regarding the onboarding and provisioning of RELIANCE services and their integration with other EOSC services, leveraging both core (cross-cutting) and selected added-value services. This task produced deliverable D6.1 - EOSC integration plan at M3, which introduced the core RELIANCE services to be onboarded in EOSC, the process to be carried out for the onboarding, the specific EOSC services to be leveraged and the roadmap for implementing the integration plan. As part of this task and in collaboration with WP5, RELIANCE deployed its AAI solution integrated with EOSC, leveraging EGI check-in service. Other services integrated and reused during this period include B2Share and Zenodo that are integrated in ROHub as repositories where researchers can publish their research object snapshots for wider dissemination and for more complex publication workflows. RELIANCE also leveraged EGI Notebooks as the default working and computing environment used by researchers to carry out their tasks; EGI DataHub to facilitate the sharing of data between scientists in the research communities, and to provide a data storage space where they can store intermediate/working data; and Argos service to create and maintain its DMP. The previous tasks required the creation of a RELIANCE community in EOSC (aka. Virtual Organisation - VO) to allow and manage access of RELIANCE users and partners to the resources allocated.</p> <p>This task also supported the deployment of service monitoring tools, backups services, helpdesk and other support channels. Finally, This task contributed to the D6.2 Annual report on EOSC operation at M12, which describes, among others, the latest state of RELIANCE services and their integration with EOSC services.</p>	

<p>Significant Results during the Year 1</p> <p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D6.1 EOSC integration plan ● Onboarding of RELIANCE services in EOSC: ROHub, ADAM (data cubes), text mining ● Integration of EOSC AAI service (EGI check-in) in ROHub IAM, which is used by all other RELIANCE services ● Integration of ROHub with Zenodo service ● Integration of ROHub with B2Share service ● Creation of RELIANCE Virtual Organisation -VO in EOSC ● Leveraging of EGI Notebooks ● Leveraging of Argos DMP service ● Leveraging of EGI DataHub within EGI Notebooks ● Supported EOSC future with demo to EC regarding EOSC services integration
<p>Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested</p> <p>No major risks have been detected during this period. Integration of most of the EOSC services was done in advance of schedule, and additional EOSC services have been reused apart from those stated in D6.1 (e.g., EGI DataHub).</p>
<p>Next Steps in Next Period</p> <p>In the next period, ROHub will integrate and support B2Drop as a default resource storage using user credentials (via the user token). This will allow the user to access the resources aggregated by his/her research objects also via the B2Drop dashboard. ROHub will allow the user to select the default storage for internal resources, so that he can choose B2Drop or one of the available S3 storages.</p> <p>RELIANCE will also assess leveraging EOSC resources, particularly EGI compute cloud. could include services for VM on demand for the scientists, and potentially for (some of the) RELIANCE services. Currently, resources are mostly provided by PSNC, however EGI compute cloud would enable the scaling-out and growing horizontally to support a larger number of users. Similarly, other EOSC support services (e.g., service monitoring, accounting and helpdesk) will be evaluated to be reused, if needed.</p>

3.6.2 Task 6.2

Task	Title
6.2	Operations and Production
Contributors	Terradue, PSNC
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
<p>During the first year of the project this task operated the core infrastructure where the common RELIANCE services were deployed, and ensured evolution in terms of reliability, performance and interoperability. The main objective of the activities undertaken was to offer the project services through the EOSC delivery channels, including the technical and service provisioning integration activities, as well as the helpdesk activities.</p>	
Significant Results during the Year 1	
<p>As significant results we can highlight:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The deployment and operation of research object platform ROHub in PSNC PaaS infrastructure, including one development instance and one production instance 	

- The deployment of ROHub service desk³ and support channels, including integration of email support@rohub.org with service desk
- The deployment and operation of research object added value services in PSNC infrastructure, including checklist service, stability service and PDF service
- The deployment and operation of the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform for the management of data cubes, including a development instance and a production instance
- The deployment and hosting of 20+ data cubes for RELIANCE communities
- The deployment and operation of the text mining and semantic enrichment services enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research.
- The leverage of EGI Notebooks , to provide RELIANCE users a flexible and scalable Jupyter Notebooks environment. This included the ordering and assignment of EGI Notebooks to RELIANCE VO
- The usage of EGI DataHub to facilitate the sharing of data between scientists in the research communities, and to provide a data storage space where they can store intermediate/working data. This included the ordering and assignment of EGI DataHub space to RELIANCE VO, and its integration in EGI Notebooks
- Provision of VMs on demand by PSNC to research communities to run and execute their own applications and tool

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

No major risks have been detected during this period.

Next Steps in Next Period

In the next period this task will continue the activities to offer the project services through the EOSC delivery channels, including the technical and service provisioning integration activities, as well as the helpdesk activities. This task will also expand the activities regarding the:

- Customization of EGI Notebooks for the needs of RELIANCE research communities, providing the possibility to load pre-configured environments with all the necessary libraries already installed.
- Increase of the resources available via EGI Notebooks in terms of number of cores and assigned RAM
- Increase of the storage space in EGI DataHub for RELIANCE VO
- Potential leverage additional EOSC resources, in particular EGI compute cloud regarding the services for VM on demand for the scientists, and/or (some of the) RELIANCE services, enabling the scaling-out and growing horizontally to support a larger number of users.
- Improvement of the maintenance procedures of RELIANCE services and potentially definition of QoS procedures

3.6.3 Task 6.3

Task	Title
6.3	Copernicus Data Pipelines
Contributors	Terradue
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
During the first year of the project this task prepared the design of Copernicus Data Pipelines and the implementation and deployment activities responding to RELIANCE users challenges. The	

³ <https://support.pcss.pl/servicedesk/customer/portal/27>

activities focused on INGV's scenarios of analysing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions and developing models and creating a new specific workflow to analyse SAR data.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- Established a collaboration with the DICE-EOSC project to provide a storage cache for specific areas identified by the GEO Geohazard Supersites.
- Access the full time series of Sentinel-1 Data (SLC) products for Geohazard Supersites locations (initially ~ 320 TB with a subsequent ~70 TB yearly volume update) through object storage accessible via HTTPS and compatible with S3.
- Ingestion and cataloguing of data (metadata extraction and publication)
- Deployment of a STAC API instance where data is being registered and made available for discovery.
- Provision of Jupyter Notebooks with several documentation and examples on how to discover, access and analyse EO products directly from a Notebook.

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

No major risks have been detected during this period.

Next Steps in Next Period

For the next period this task will continue the Supersites data storage population and deployment of the Kubernetes processing cluster. The showcase from the GEO Geohazard Supersites community will :

- Define an OGC Application Package
- Test and validate Application Deployment in PSNC (.. and EOSC)
- Document the full cycle as research object
- Deliver long time series data to a data cube

3.7 WP7 – Case studies and EOSC interaction

Scientific communities involved in WP7 (CNR, UiO, INGV) defined the scientific **scenarios** to be implemented by using the RELIANCE services to demonstrate the efficacy of the services within EOSC. Six scenarios were designed concerning the Multidisciplinary case studies on 2020 lockdown and involving the Sea Monitoring community (CNR) and the Atmospheric and Climate modeling community (UiO) and 12 multidisciplinary scenarios related to Earth science grand challenges by the three scientific communities involved (including the Geohazard community represented by INGV).

Before implementing the scenarios, the scientific communities defined a list of **requirements** needed to successfully replicate the research workflows formalized in the 18 scenarios. The requirements address all the RELIANCE services, in particular, the RELIANCE webpage, the ROHub user interface, the ADAM Platform and the data cube technology, the JupyterHub and Notebook, the Text mining and Enrichment tools, the Galaxy platform and other EOSC services and infrastructures. The list of requirements has been discussed during specific telcos and hackathons, and agreed with the technical partners of the project. The result of this work is available in the Deliverable 7.1 - Paragraph 5 “Requirements - RELIANCE Services”, where the entire list with specifications, sources, types and status of each requirement is reported.

The scientific communities made a list of necessary **datasets** to be included in the ADAM platform and used to implement the scenarios. A total of 51 datasets were included in the ADAM Platform and made available as data cubes.

Currently, most of the technical requirements have been satisfied and the scientific communities fully implemented all scenarios planned for the Task 7.1 and part of the scenarios planned for the Task 7.2, producing **25** research objects (ROs). Furthermore, **1000+ ROs** were implemented following automatic procedures to generate ROs. This was important to have not only a number of high-quality research objects (generated by T7.1 and T7.2) but also to have a significant base of research objects and related resources that could be leveraged by other researchers. CNR ISMAR produced 49 bibliographic ROs starting from a research on the Web of Science⁴ about the 2020 lockdown. The research identified 49 papers dealing with Earth Sciences and the consequences on the environment. Each paper has the relative RO enriched by means of the text mining tool extracting metadata automatically. The bibliographic ROs will be analysed with the recommendation services in the next period.

INGV produced 850+ massive bibliographic ROs from three different scenarios. The first category of ROs document the monitoring activity of the most active volcanoes in Italy from weekly reports⁵, while the others exploit the Italian seismic catalogue⁶ to collect the seismicity at Mt Etna volcano (Italy) and to document the strongest earthquakes of the world since the 1980s. Other massive ROs related to automatic mapping of volcanic eruptions will be generated in the next period.

UiO has chosen to create massive ROs exploiting existing Research data from the Norwegian National Research Data Archive⁷. 88 ROs have been identified, all related to the Climate Community. These ROs have been generated on the development instance of ROHub, and shortly they will be in production.

It is important to highlight the role of RELIANCE services, in particular the ROHub API and the semantic enrichment service, which allowed the generation of ROs automatically and at large scale, without big efforts. The code for generating some of these ROs are available online as Jupyter Notebooks⁸ or python scripts⁹. Moreover, that generation of these ROs automatically was carried out through a well-defined process, where each research community was assigned a technical partner to support them in the automatic generation of their ROs.

3.7.1 Task 7.1

Task	Title
7.1	Multidisciplinary case study on 2020 Lockdown consequences on the environment
Contributors	CNR, UiO, INGV
Summary of Progress during Year 1	
During the first year of the project the scientific communities produced the following scenarios about the case study “Multidisciplinary case study on 2020 Lockdown consequences on the environment”:	
GC0-SC1 “Bibliography analysis on lockdown related papers within Earth science” (CNR)	
GC0-SC2 “Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause” (CNR)	
GC0-SC3 “Impact of the Covid-19 Lockdown on Air quality” (UiO)	
GC0-SC4 “Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space” (CNR)	
GC0-SC5 “Underwater Sound Pressure Level Analysis” (CNR)	

⁴ <https://www.webofscience.com/>

⁵ <https://www.ct.ingv.it/index.php/monitoraggio-e-sorveglianza/prodotti-del-monitoraggio/bollettini-settimanali-multidisciplinari>

⁶ <http://terremoti.ingv.it/>

⁷ <https://archive.sigma2.no/>

⁸ https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks/tree/main/RO_generation

⁹ <https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/UPM-Massive-ROs-Creator>

GC0-SC6 “SNAPSHOT: Lockdown impacts on on the Northern Adriatic Sea at selected site: AcquaAlta Platform Water quality (CNR)

From the implementation of the scenarios, 15 ROs have been created:

RO1-GC0-SC1 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/7f025f6e-9835-4af8-aa48-0152474eda37>

RO2-GC0-SC1 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/629b2be8-2457-44e9-bf8f-8aaba3fde6a8>

RO1-GC0-SC2 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/49f52ad4-bf2c-4f50-9242-a26962d5a7a2>

RO1-GC0-SC3 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/374d0d3a-4807-4925-be83-b9eea52356e3>

RO2-GC0-SC3 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/53aa90bf-c593-4e6d-923f-d4711ac4b0e1>

RO3-GC0-SC3 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/67edd16f-c3d8-4879-a3a5-2d223e7dce6d>

RO4-GC0-SC3 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/5f2e7ab8-8122-41b3-8d53-060e09855fa7>

RO5-GC0-SC3 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/d767e6c3-6cfd-4e68-a989-0b4cbe9236b5>

RO6-GC0-SC3 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/66613047-4680-459d-8c60-509c349830d5>

RO1-GC0-SC4 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/894d3a33-8340-497d-beaf-5b9d85c9bfc7>

RO2-GC0-SC4 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/34d648b3-0014-4a19-8469-40b9380ca4c3>

RO3-GC0-SC4 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/d0694eaf-a561-4c9f-9a70-17c296da2140>

RO1-GC0-SC5 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/6640422d-57ed-4814-b0d0-8eb4ee85f501>

RO2-GC0-SC5 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/3f68f32e-1b6d-4689-acee-b797ba2c8429>

RO1-GC0-SC6 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/0869e396-3733-4aff-8fb2-94c8937b28aa>

ROs have been generated using both methods implemented in the RELIANCE project, that are the new ROHub user interface and the ROHub libraries for the Jupyter Notebook. Earth scientists have access to a Jupyter Notebook environment provided by EGI in the EOSC and used to implement the workflow included in the ROs (RO2-GC0-SC3, RO4-GC0-SC3, RO5-GC0-SC3, RO2-GC0-SC4, RO1-GC0-SC5, RO2-GC0-SC5, RO1-GC0-SC6). The ADAM Platform has been used in scenarios GC0-SC3 and GC0-SC4, the Galaxy platform has been used in Scenario GC0-SC3.

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- the table of requirements needed to finalize or improve the RELIANCE services by the technical partners;
- the EGI Jupyter notebook available in a common workspace by the scientific community to implement the common scenarios;
- 15 new datasets integrated in ADAM for this task;
- 15 multidisciplinary ROs created to study the 2020 lockdown consequences on the environment

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested

No are no deviation and corrective actions needed

Next Steps in Next Period

The RELIANCE team will expand the Earth Science use cases to include new case studies across societal/economical domains using data coming from non-Earth Science stakeholders. Additional databases including for instance economic data will be integrated and RELIANCE services will be extended to non-ES communities for further adoption. The onboarding of the new non-ES community will be done in the next months thanks to an open call and will foster the demonstration of the system’s capacity to sustain joint research among heterogeneous communities.

3.7.1 Task 7.2

Task	Title
7.1	Earth Science communities case studies
Contributors	CNR, UiO, INGV

Summary of Progress during Year 1

During the first year of the project, one scenario linked to the **Grand Challenge 2** about the loss of biodiversity and sustainability (biodiversity, fisheries, marine litter) has been formalized:

GC2-SC1 “Mapping the Mediterranean photic zone” (CNR)

and two ROs have been produced:

RO1-GC2-SC1 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/1c87c3d6-46f0-4bfe-bc73-88282fb8c3c5>

RO2-GC2-SC1 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/f9fca558-8f1d-4aab-a53b-90c4d1bc0037>

The scenarios dealing with the **Grand Challenge 3** “Extreme weather events and climate adaptation (biomass)” are four:

GC3-SC1 “Spatial and temporal distribution of CWC in the Mediterranean Sea” (CNR)

GC3-SC2 “Reindeer husbandry in the changing climate” (UiO)

GC3-SC1 “Arctic browning and winter warming” (UiO)

GC3-SC1 “Impact of climate extremes on vegetation dynamics in multiple dynamic vegetation models and their future projections” (UiO)

INGV implemented the seven scenarios dealing with the **Grand Challenge 4** about the reducing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions:

GC4-SC1 “Analysis of surface deformations at active volcanoes” (INGV)

GC4-SC2 “Models of the volcanic plumbing system” (INGV)

GC4-SC3 “Mapping emissions of volcanic eruptions from space” (INGV)

GC4-SC4 “Massive & automatic RO scenario: imaging of volcano eruptive plumes” (INGV)

GC4-SC5 “Massive & automatic RO scenario: INGV reports of Italian Volcanoes” (INGV)

GC4-SC6 “Massive & automatic RO scenario: seismic activity at Mt Etna volcano (Italy)” (INGV)

GC4-SC7 “Massive & automatic RO scenario: high magnitude Mediterranean and global seismic events”

Five ROs have been generated from the scenario GC4-SC2 with application to several volcanoes of the world. The open access code runs in the EGI’s Jupyter notebook environment and the ROs have been created using the ROHub APIs. With the support of the technical partners involved in RELIANCE, in the first period of the project part of the massive and automatic scenarios have been implemented, generating 740 ROs from scenarios GC4-SC5, GC4-SC6 and GC4-SC7. ROs from the scenario GC4-SC2, a template RO for GC4-SC4, and one single example for each of the abovementioned massive scenarios produced are:

RO1-GC4-SC2 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/d86d66ff-c096-4e78-b02a-95cfeba21e35>

RO2-GC4-SC2 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/6d6e540b-1b52-4ad1-8906-33d3144fce68>

RO3-GC4-SC2 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/09d35670-c07e-41f2-94f9-c58119e33b60>

RO4-GC4-SC2 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/0938a79e-f5a6-4481-b01a-a82e17f7d51a>

RO5-GC4-SC2 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/cdcd3c0a-f280-40de-93e6-9a4ba2be6f67>

RO1-GC4-SC4 <https://w3id.org/ro-id/c9d776f7-58a2-4576-b4c1-65913d1dd896>

RO1-GC4-SC5 http://sandbox.rohub.org/rodl/ROs/Etna_bulletin_20210607_20210613/

RO1-GC4-SC6 http://sandbox.rohub.org/rodl/ROs/Etna_seismicity_20150112_20150124/

RO1-GC4-SC7 http://sandbox.rohub.org/rodl/ROs/earthquake_20210521_180415_qinghai_china/

Significant Results during the Year 1

As significant results we can highlight:

- the table of requirements needed to finalize or improve the RELIANCE services by the technical partners;
- the EGI Jupyter notebook available in a common workspace by the scientific community to implement the common scenarios;
- 24 new datasets integrated in ADAM for this task;
- 12 Earth Science ROs created, plus 850+ massive and automatic ROs

Risks, Deviations from the Description of Action and Corrective Actions Taken/Suggested
No are no deviation and corrective actions needed
Next Steps in Next Period
For the next period, further ROs on Grand challenges 2 and 3 and 4 are going to be created following the scientific activity described in the scenarios already formalized. New scenarios could be added in the three challenges after the involvement of non-ES communities.

4 Conclusions

As explained in the previous chapters, RELIANCE project managed to achieve all milestones, except the launch of the open call which was shifted to M15 as explained in WP2 report. These milestones include:

- Kick-off meeting
- Onboarding of the RELIANCE services in EOSC
- Release of the project communication plan
- Project management setup, including the configuration and deployment of all the communication tools and channels, the project Website and the release of the project management handbook.
- Models and resources adaptation to EOSC
- Data management plan and initial data cubes
- RELIANCE services integrated in EOSC v1, outreach & multi-disciplinary research from use cases

Moreover, RELIANCE submitted 17 Deliverables in the first year. This has shown to be a demanding task, and the consortium finds it to be a success, as most of the delays were due to overlapping in Deliverable planning, ending up with several being scheduled for the same date, or overlapping with the holiday season. Two deliverables were shifted: this document (D1.3) as it includes a detailed progress report for each work package until (and including) M12, and D2.7 which was shifted mostly due to activities related to preparation of the EOSC Future INFRAEOSC07 projects Multi-lateral Collaboration Agreement, and the alignment of RELIANCE with the EOSC Future & INFRAEOSC-07-2020 projects collaboration topics. Both delays were agreed with the PO. Apart from that, in general no other deviations or corrective actions were needed.

A number of important outputs were already produced, as well as plans and strategies for continuation of work and collaboration of partners in general. The RELIANCE services are all in production state and have been integrated with other EOSC services, even ahead of schedule and we have leveraged more EOSC services than envisioned in the proposal preparation. As a consequence, we have been able to offer demos and support use cases for EOSC Future and DICE Ask Me Anything Session. Moreover, we have been strongly active in the EOSC ecosystem, participating and contributing to multiple working groups, task forces and collaboration agreements. This has been a much higher effort than originally planned, but it has allowed us to align better with all other projects and promote our services. We have been able also to give already various demos of our services by real scientists (in real life scenarios) to multiple audiences, which has brought a lot of attention¹⁰.

The dissemination of the project was focused on promoting the project and our services in different events, and in reaching the target audiences, and, in the following period, we will be working on extending our user communities and involve others via the open call and the collaboration with other

¹⁰ See for example this RO created by Anne Fouilloux (one of our scientists in RELIANCE) <https://w3id.org/ro-id/f1bbcdad-2af1-44ec-9304-387b63ad0884>

EOSC projects. The dissemination and community-building activities also generated a series of info/promo videos, which were not originally planned, in order to ease new scientists to understand and engage with our services. Additionally, multiple connections with other EOSC related projects and EOSC relevant bodies have been established as planned. Thus, the consortium considers the project to be on track and has successfully started the second year of its implementation.